

A Coarse-Grained Discrete Element Model (CG-DEM) based on parameter scaling for dense wet granular system

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HIGHLIGHTS

- CG-DEM for wet particles in a drum is explored in rolling and wet slumping regimes.
- Scaling rules for dry forces and liquid bridge related parameters are reviewed and tested.
- The CG-DEM model can reproduce most of the system's macroscopic rheological state variables.
- Scalings based on invariant and variable coefficient of restitution are compared for the dry case.
- The effect of CG modelling on the liquid convection and migration is studied.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The Discrete Element Model (DEM) is widely used for studying wet granular systems, where particles experience liquid bridge forces. However, due to its high computational cost, DEM is not a viable approach for industrial scale simulations. A potential solution is offered by coarse-graining (CG), where a group of particles is substituted by a larger particle, thereby increasing the computational efficiency of the simulations. However, it is essential to consider appropriate scaling rules to properly apply CG-DEM and conserve the material's rheological behaviour.

Two scaling approaches based on constant dimensionless groups, Weber (We) and Bond (Bo) numbers, are compared. The We-based CG-DEM simulation can reproduce the volume fraction, velocity, apparent viscosity and macroscopic friction fields properly, but not granular temperature. The effect of CG on the liquid convection and migration patterns, as well as wall coverage is explored. In addition, the applicability of the CG-DEM model in the wet slumping regime is investigated.

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1. Introduction

Wet particle systems are of great importance in industrial processes, such as coating and granulation, as well as in natural phenomena, such as landslides. In these systems, the presence of liquid leads to the formation of bridges between the particles. The resulting cohesive forces, have a considerable effect on the mechanical behaviour of the system [1,2].

It has been reported that a large part of worldwide energy is wasted because undesired and misunderstood particle phenomena, leading to reduced performance of industrial plants [3]. It is desirable to lower the global energy consumption by optimizing particulate processes, including wet particle systems. However, trial-and-error experiments need large time, energy, and material consumption. The Discrete Element Model (DEM) is proved to be a valuable tool for predicting the behaviour of granular systems and obtaining data at the particle level [4]. One major limitation of DEM is the high computational cost, when simulating industrial scale systems with millions or many more particles [5].

In addition to the advancement in hardware technology, coarse-graining (CG), can significantly increase the computational efficiency of DEM simulations [5,6]. In this approach, groups of particles are represented by ℓ times larger particles. This allows not only decreasing the number of particles, but also increasing the time-step. CG-DEM has been used to study different applications including, fluidization [7], mixing [8], and pneumatic conveying [5]. However, to ensure the agreement between the flow behaviour of the original (primary) particle simulation and the CG particle simulation, one has to consider appropriate scaling rules for the interaction forces [9,10]. Sakai and Koshizuka [5] proposed that the contact force between CG particles must be scaled as ℓ^3 times the contact force acting on colliding original particles. Radl et al. [11], derived the scaling rules for the contact parameters by non-dimensionalizing the equation of motion in the normal direction, which leads to ℓ^2 times scaling of the contact forces. The same scaling (ℓ^2) has been proposed by Chan and Washino [12] considering the balance of interaction forces on the interface of a chosen control volume in the bulk of particles.

Different scaling rules have been proposed based on the powder material, namely cohesive [6,13], or frictional [14], and the flow regime, namely dense sheared [15–17], or dynamic, dilute fluidized [5,18–20].

To our knowledge, only few studies have been conducted on CG-DEM wet particle systems. Chan and Washino [12], as example, used the direct force scaling CG model introduced by Sakai et al. [21] for a dense and dynamic system of wet particles with pendular (binary) liquid bridges, in a vertical blade mixer. They used quadratic scaling (ℓ^2) for both contact and liquid bridge forces, and showed the ability of the CG model to capture the mixing behaviour. Tausendschön et al. [10] studied four different parameter scaling strategies, namely dimensionless overlap-based, stress-based, coefficient of restitution-based, and Bond number-based scaling, for cohesive wet powders in a gas-solid fluidized bed. They concluded that the first three strategies (leading to ℓ^2 scaling) agree better with the original system than the Bond number based scaling (leading to ℓ^3 scaling) in terms of average particle-fluid relative velocity. Hu et al. [22] proposed the quadratic scaling (ℓ^2) for both inter-particle (contact and cohesive) force and torque. They evaluated the validity of the CG-DEM model based on geometric similarity in a vertical mixer and observed a good agreement with the original particle simulations in terms of probability density function of particle velocity. Kosaku et al. [23] derived a cubic scaling (ℓ^3) for the contact forces and a quadratic scaling (ℓ^2) for the capillary forces based on JKR theory. They reported a good agreement between the scaled and original DEM simulations in terms of the lifted height and cascading angle of the powder bed, in contrast with the above-mentioned studies where the quadratic scaling of the contact forces was found the most appropriate approach.

This study investigates the scaling rules for dense dry and wet particle systems in a rotating drum via CG-DEM simulations. Depending on the drum angular velocity, filling level, and the wall friction, different regimes, including slipping, slumping, rolling, cascading, and cataracting can occur [24]. We focus on the rolling regime for wet systems and extend the analysis to the wet slumping regime [25]. As a preliminary step, the effect of damping coefficient scaling on the behaviour of the CG model is investigated in the dry case. Furthermore, the scaling rules for liquid bridge forces based on two dimensionless numbers, namely, Weber number and Bond number, are discussed and compared with other scaling models, resulting in unification. The accuracy of CG simulations is assessed via the comparison of macroscopic flow and bulk properties, obtained by discrete to continuum averaging. Additionally, the validity of CG-DEM in the case of liquid migration is investigated using the model proposed by Mani et al. [26]. To our knowledge, it is the first time that the applicability of CG modelling for liquid migration in a dense shear system is studied and discussed in such detail. The influence of CG on wall coverage by the particles is an additional aspect studied. Finally, the applicability of the CG model in the wet slumping regime is considered, which is more intermittent in nature than rolling.

The paper is organized as follows: In Section 2, after introducing DEM for wet particle systems, the simulation set up and the averaging methodology for the macroscopic quantities of interest are discussed. Subsequently, the fundamentals of the CG model for dry and wet particles are presented in Sections 3 and 4, respectively. The paper follows with discussions on the results obtained from the performed CG-DEM simulations in Section 5, and it ends with the summary and conclusion in Section 6.

2. DEM simulation

DEM is a Lagrangian numerical approach widely used for the simulation of granular systems. In DEM, the translational and rotational motion of the spherical particles are described by

$$m_i \frac{dv_i}{dt} = \sum_j f_{ij} + m_i g \quad (1)$$

and

$$I_i \frac{d\omega_i}{dt} = T_i, \quad (2)$$

where m_i is the particle mass, I_i is the moment of inertia, v_i is the translational velocity of particle i , f_{ij} is the contact force between particles i and j , T_i is the total torque on particle i , and ω_i is its angular velocity.

A linear viscoelastic contact model in the normal direction (which is enforced to be always repulsive), with a viscoelastic slider in the tangential direction, is used to describe the interaction between particles. The contact forces in normal and tangential directions are given by:

$$f_{ij}^n = k_n \delta_n \mathbf{n}_{ij} + c_n \dot{\delta}_n \mathbf{n}_{ij}, \quad (3)$$

$$f_{ij}^t = \min(|f_{ij}^n| \mu_p \mathbf{t}_{ij}, k_t \delta_t \mathbf{t}_{ij} + c_t \dot{\delta}_t \mathbf{t}_{ij}) \quad (4)$$

where k_n , k_t , c_n , c_t are the contact normal stiffness, tangential stiffness, normal and tangential damping coefficients, respectively. μ_p represents the friction coefficient and δ_n , δ_t , \mathbf{n}_{ij} , and \mathbf{t}_{ij} are the elastic normal particle overlap, the elastic tangential displacement, the unit normal and the unit tangential vectors between particles i and j . For details, see Smilauer et al. [27]. The simulation time step is calculated based on the half-period of the normal direction vibration of a harmonic oscillator around its equilibrium position:

$$\Delta t_c \leq 1/50t_c, \quad t_c = \pi / \sqrt{(k_n/m_{ij}) - (c_n/2m_{ij})^2} \quad (5)$$

where $m_{ij} = \frac{m_i m_j}{m_i + m_j}$ is the reduced mass.

Fig. 1. Schematic of a linear viscoelastic normal contact force model combined with a capillary force.

2.1. Liquid bridge physics

It is assumed that in the initial configuration, the liquid layer homogeneously covers the entire surface of the particles. For each particle, the liquid film volume is proportional to the particle volume. When two wet particles collide, part of the liquid content from each particle is devoted to create a liquid bridge among them. An additional liquid bridge force must be added to the normal force to account for such physics. Fig. 1 shows the schematic of such combined model for wet particles. After the collision of two wet particles, they experience an attractive kick-in force to $-f_a$ at $\delta = 0$, and then a linear viscoelastic behaviour (loading path), until they start to rebound (unloading path). When the particles start to get separated ($\delta \leq 0$), the cohesive capillary force (f_{cap}) keeps the interaction active, until the separation distance exceeds the critical rupture distance (S_c). In this study, relatively low water content is used to ensure the formation of only binary bridges among the particles (pendular regime).

The liquid bridge force consists of capillary and viscous terms. The capillary forces model proposed by Rabinovich et al. [28] and corrected by Lambert et al. [29] is adopted:

$$f_{cap} = -2\pi R\gamma \cos \theta \left(1 + \frac{a_n}{2h}\right), \quad (6)$$

$$h = \frac{a_n}{2} \left(-1 + \sqrt{1 + \frac{V_b}{\pi R a_n^2}}\right), \quad (7)$$

where $R = 2R_i R_j / (R_i + R_j)$, R_i and R_j are the radii of particles i and j , a_n is the inter-particle separation distance, θ is the solid-liquid contact angle, V_b is the liquid bridge volume, and γ the liquid surface tension.

The classical expression for the normal viscous force by Happel and Brenner [30] is used in the simulations:

$$f_{vis} = \frac{3}{2} R^2 \eta \frac{\dot{\delta}_n}{a_n + a_{n0}}, \quad (8)$$

where η is the liquid viscosity. To avoid the divergence of the viscous force when the separation distance tends to zero, a characteristic length (a_{n0}), as proposed by Trung Vo et al. [31], is considered in the denominator.

Once the particles reach a critical distance (S_c), the liquid bridge ruptures. Based on [32], the dimensionless critical rupture distance ($S_c^* = S_c/R$) is:

$$2S_c^* = (1 + 0.5\theta)(V^*1/3 + 0.1V^*2/3), \quad (9)$$

where $V^* = V_b/R^3$ is the dimensionless liquid bridge volume.

Table 1
Default parameters used in the DEM simulations.

Default parameters used in the DEM simulations.	
Particle density (ρ_p)	3000 [kg/m ³]
Original particle diameter (d_p)	0.001 [m]
Normal contact stiffness (k_n)	100 [N/m]
Tangential contact stiffness (k_t)	30 [N/m]
Damping coefficient (c_n, c_t)	0.008 [Ns/m]
Liquid surface tension (γ)	0.073 [N/m]
Liquid viscosity (η)	0.001 [Pa s]
Contact angle (θ)	0.0 [°]
Liquid to solid ratio (V_f/V_p)	0.02 [-]
Coefficient of friction (μ_p)	0.9 [-]
Time step (Δt)	5×10^{-6} [s]
Number of (original) particles (N_p)	360,000 [-]
Geometry parameters	
Drum diameter (D)	0.2 [m]
Drum length (L)	0.06 [m]
Baffle number (n_b)	48 [-]
Baffle height (n_i)	0.001 [m]
Drum angular velocity (ω)	0.45 [rad/s]

2.1.1. Liquid migration

In the most general case, the liquid associated to each particle at the beginning remains constant during the simulation. If liquid migration is active, the liquid can redistribute, leading to variable volume of liquid film on the particles and liquid bridges of different volume. The liquid migration model, as proposed by Mani et al. [26], is adopted in parts of this study. Based on this model, local liquid transfer occurs when the particles collide, or detach from one another as sketched in Fig. 2. Upon the collision of particles i and j having liquid film volumes of $V_{f,i}$ and $V_{f,j}$, respectively, a liquid bridge of volume $V_{b,ij} = \min(V_{f,i} + V_{f,j}, V_{max})$ forms, with $V_{max} = \beta R_p$ set as threshold to avoid a transition to the funicular state. To ensure conservation of total liquid volume, if V_{max} is reached, the remaining liquid is added to the liquid films $V_{f,i}$ and $V_{f,j}$ [33]. When particles i and j reach the critical distance under unloading, the liquid bridge ruptures. The liquid volume $V_{b,ij}$ splits in half between particles i and j and each part distributes among the liquid bridges of the contacts of particles i and j respectively. The resulting liquid bridge between particle i and its neighbour k , $V_{b,i-k}^{new}$ is:

$$V_{b,i-k}^{new} = \min \left(V_{b,i-k}^{old} + \frac{V_{b,ij}}{2N_{c,i}}, V_{max} \right), \quad (10)$$

where $N_{c,i}$ represents the number of the contacts of particle i .

Other mechanisms that would lead to a change in the liquid bridge volume, such as evaporation and condensation, are assumed not to occur in the system.

2.2. Simulation set up and geometry

Simulations are performed using YADE open source DEM framework [27,34] in a rotating drum of diameter D and length L . Fig. 3(b) shows the drum geometry, which is created using Blender software and imported in YADE.

Periodic boundaries are adapted in the axial direction. Parameters for the basic set of simulations with 360,000 mono-disperse particles, and water as the liquid, are displayed in Table 1. Some of these parameters are then varied in Section 5 to explore their influence on CG scaling. To avoid wall slip, small baffles (lifters) are added to the drum wall. The effect of baffles size and a number of process and material parameters is studied in Appendix A. Particle-wall cohesion is deactivated in order to keep all particles in the bulk for a better analysis (except for Section 5.2.1). The drum angular velocity is set, such that the regime is rolling.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the liquid migration model proposed by Mani et al. [26].

Fig. 3. (a) 2D view of the drum geometry. C represents the centre of the drum located at $(0.1,0.1,0.03)$, and the dash lines show the selected slice of the drum $0.120 < x < 0.124$ m. (b) 3D view of the drum with particles at the bottom.

2.3. Averaging from micro to macro

In order to access and study macroscopic kinematic and stress fields, 2-D spatio-temporal averaging like in [35] is applied. The spatial averaging is performed over a grid of 48-by-48 cuboid volumes, i.e. approximately 92,098 original, 23,160 CG2, 9602 CG3 particles in a cell. For the temporal averaging, 100 snapshots in the steady state with a sampling time step of $t_s = 0.05$ s are used, unless specified otherwise.

2.3.1. Macroscopic quantities of interest

The cell-averaged bulk density is:

$$\langle \rho \rangle = \frac{1}{V} \sum_{i \in V} m_i = \rho_p \phi, \quad (11)$$

with mass m_i , V volume of the cell, particle density ρ_p , and volume fraction ϕ . The brackets indicate both cell- and time-averaging in steady state.

The cell-averaged velocity is defined as:

$$\langle v \rangle = \frac{1}{\langle \rho \rangle V} \sum_{i \in V} m_i v_i \quad (12)$$

with particle velocity v_i .

The strain rate tensor is given by

$$\langle \dot{\epsilon}_{\alpha\beta} \rangle = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i \in V} (\nabla_\beta v_{i,\alpha} + \nabla_\alpha v_{i,\beta}), \quad (13)$$

with particle velocity v_i , and Greek letters represent the coordinate system's components.

We can then define the fluctuation of the velocity components as

$$\langle v_\alpha'^2 \rangle = \langle v_\alpha^2 \rangle - \langle v_\alpha \rangle^2, \quad (14)$$

and the granular temperature is:

$$\langle T_g \rangle = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{\alpha=1}^3 \langle v_\alpha'^2 \rangle \quad (15)$$

The stress tensor is given by

$$\langle \sigma_{\alpha\beta} \rangle = \frac{1}{V} \left[\sum_{i \in V} m_i v'_{i,\alpha} v'_{i,\beta} - \sum_{c \in V} l_\alpha^c f_\beta^c \right], \quad (16)$$

with contact c , force f^c , and branch vector l^c . V represents the volume of the cell. The local macroscopic bulk friction coefficient is defined as the ratio of the deviatoric stress to pressure:

$$\langle \mu \rangle = \langle \sigma_{dev} \rangle / \langle p \rangle, \quad (17)$$

with $p = \sigma_{\alpha\alpha}/3$. The deviatoric part of a tensor \mathbf{Q} , quantifies anisotropy, defined as

$$Q_{dev} = \sqrt{\frac{(Q_1 - Q_2)^2 + (Q_2 - Q_3)^2 + (Q_3 - Q_1)^2}{6}}, \quad (18)$$

in terms of the eigen values Q_1 , Q_2 , and Q_3 . The apparent viscosity is given by the ratio of the deviatoric stress to deviatoric strain rate as:

$$\langle \eta \rangle = \langle \sigma_{dev} \rangle / \langle \dot{\gamma} \rangle, \quad (19)$$

with $\dot{\gamma} = \dot{\epsilon}_{dev}$.

The inertial number estimates the local rapidity of the flow and can be defined as the ratio between pressure and shear rate time scales [36]:

$$I = \langle \dot{\gamma} \rangle d \sqrt{\langle \rho \rangle / \langle p \rangle}. \quad (20)$$

In the following, the averaging symbol $\langle \rangle$ will be omitted. General and more advanced micro-to-macro definitions of the bulk macroscopic quantities including volume fraction (ϕ), velocity (v), pressure (p), stress (τ), and deviatoric strain rate ($\dot{\gamma}$), designed to be compatible with continuum balance equations, can be found in [36–41]. We compared the different averaging approaches in a few cases (data not shown) and observed only minor differences, so that we stick to the somewhat simpler cell-averaging.

3. Coarse-grained DEM for dry particles

Coarse-grained DEM is a numerical upscaling approach used to decrease the high computational cost of DEM simulations. The size of particles is enlarged ℓ times, so that each enlarged particle (CG) represents ℓ^3 original particles ($R_{CG} = \ell R_p$). This approach is based on the postulate that the macro fields and balance equations should be invariant on the following levels:

- Level 0: Mass (originates from $m_p v_p^0$) and moment of inertia I_p (from $I_p \omega_p^0$)
- Level 1: Translational momentum (from $m_p v_p^1$) and angular momentum (from $I_p \omega_p^1$)
- Level 2: Translational kinetic energy (from $m_p v_p^2$) and rotational kinetic energy (from $I_p \omega_p^2$)

To fulfil mass equivalence across the scales (level 0), considering the same volume fractions, $\langle \phi_{CG} \rangle = \langle \phi_p \rangle$, and the same density for the original and CG particles ($\rho_{CG} = \rho_p$), each CG particle will include ℓ^3 original particles: ($m_{CG} = m_p \ell^3$).

To have equivalent momentum balance (level 1), the averaged translational velocity of the CG particles must be equal to the velocity of the original particle, $\langle v_{CG} \rangle = \langle v_p \rangle$.

The total translational kinetic energy in the system includes the following terms:

$$E_{tot}^k = E_{average}^k + E_{fluctuation}^k, \quad (21)$$

where $E_{average}^k$ is the translational kinetic energy of the particles due to the convective motion and $E_{fluctuation}^k$ is the kinetic energy due to the translational fluctuation velocity of the particles. $E_{average}^k$ is expected to be conserved based on the mass and momentum conservation. Given the equivalence of velocity (level 1) and kinetic energy between the scales (level 2), in order to obtain matching of the total kinetic energy $\langle E_{tot,p}^k \rangle = \langle E_{tot,CG}^k \rangle$, the velocity fluctuations should be the same in CG and the original systems, $v_p' = v_p - \langle v_p \rangle = v_{CG}' = v_{CG} - \langle v_{CG} \rangle$. This leads to:

$$\langle v_{CG}'^2 \rangle = \langle (v_{CG}' + \langle v \rangle)^2 \rangle = \langle v_{CG}'^2 \rangle + \langle v \rangle^2 = \langle v_p'^2 \rangle + \langle v \rangle^2 = \langle v_p'^2 \rangle. \quad (22)$$

However, as reported by Radl et al. [11] and Benyahia and Galvin [42], granular temperature, which is proportional to the square of

the velocity fluctuations, cannot be conserved in CG simulations, because the fluctuation energy between the primary particles within CG particles is neglected.

Concerning the rotational motion, the angular velocity of the particles is obtained based on the equivalence of rotational kinetic energy, with upscaled moment of inertia $I_{CG} = \ell^5 m_p R_p^2 = \ell^5 I_p$:

$$R_{CG} \omega_{CG} = R_p \omega_p \text{ and } \omega_{CG} = \ell^{-1} \omega_p. \quad (23)$$

Considering the balance of contact forces on the interface of a control volume in a dense granular system, contact forces should scale ℓ^2 times in the CG simulations $f_{CG} = \ell^2 f_p$ [12] which implies also equivalence of stress $\langle \sigma_{CG} \rangle = \langle \sigma_p \rangle$.

Based on a linear contact model, as in Eq. (3), considering geometric similarity of the normal contact overlaps ($\delta_{n,CG} = \ell \delta_n$) [11], ℓ times scaling of the stiffness is derived ($k_{n,CG} = \ell k_n$).

The scaling of the damping coefficient in,

$$c_n = \sqrt{\frac{4m_{ij}k_n}{1 + (\pi/\ln e_n)^2}}, \quad (24)$$

depends on whether the restitution coefficient is kept constant. In that case, c_n scales ℓ^2 times, $c_{n,CG} = \ell^2 c_{n,p}$.

Considering an invariant coefficient of restitution, the time step of the simulations scales ℓ times:

$$\Delta t_{CG} = \ell \Delta t \quad (25)$$

While the assumption $e_{n,CG} = e_{n,p}$ can be a good choice for dilute systems [43], it might be questionable for dense particle systems. Nakamura et al. [15] proposed the scaling rule $e_{n,CG} = \sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{\ell}(1 - e_{n,p}^2)}$, based on constant dissipation of energy. Based on the scaled restitution coefficient, the damping coefficient can be calculated using Eq. (24). CG simulations based on constant and scaled restitution coefficients are compared in Section 5.1.

4. CG for wet particle systems

Implementing a CG model for wet particle systems requires additional considerations for the liquid bridge related parameters. Table 2 summarizes existing studies about the CG-DEM modelling of wet cohesive particle systems and the scaling approaches adopted for inter-particle forces, torque (T), lengths (normal overlap and liquid bridge rupture distance).

In this study, the CG simulations are tested based on the considerations described in the following.

4.1. Liquid bridge volume

In order to conserve the amount of liquid present in the system, the liquid volume assigned to each CG particle ($V_{f,p}$) is taken as ℓ^3 times the liquid assigned to the original particles:

$$V_{f,CG} = \ell^3 V_{f,p}, \quad (26)$$

Consequently, the dimensionless relative liquid bridge volume is constant:

$$V_{f,CG}/R_{CG}^3 = V_{f,p}/R_p^3 = V^*, \quad (27)$$

4.2. Rupture distance

According to the rupture model proposed by Willett et al. [32], the dimensionless liquid bridge rupture distance is a function of the dimensionless liquid bridge volume in Eq. (9), so that, using Eq. (27), we obtain:

$$S_{c,CG}/R_{CG} = S_c/R_p = S_c^*, \quad (28)$$

Table 2
Recent literature on CG-DEM of wet particle systems.

Author, year	Scaling based on constant	f^n	f_{cap}, f_{vis}	T	Geometric similarity ^a	Application
Chan et al. 2018	f/R^2	ℓ^2	ℓ^2	ℓ^3	No	Vertical blade mixer
Tausendschön et al. 2020	δ_n^*	ℓ^2	ℓ^2	ℓ^3	Yes	Fluidized bed
Tausendschön et al. 2020	Bo	ℓ^3	ℓ^3	ℓ^4	Yes	Fluidized bed
Hu et al. 2022	Energy	ℓ^2	ℓ^2	ℓ^2	Yes	Vertical blade mixer
Kosaku et al. 2023	Energy	ℓ^3	ℓ^2	ℓ^4	Yes/No ^b	Pan pelletizer

^a Equivalence of dimensionless contact normal overlap as well as dimensionless rupture distance between the CG and original particles.

^b Yes for rupture distance/ No for contact normal overlap.

which corresponds to the scaling of rupture distance according to geometric similarity, as:

$$S_{c,CG} = \ell S_c. \quad (29)$$

4.3. Liquid bridge force scaling

The dynamic behaviour of the wet particles in the drum is defined by three contributions, contact forces, liquid bridge forces, and gravitational forces, resulting in dimensionless groups. The scaling of liquid bridge forces, capillary and viscous forces can be tuned based on the conservation of specific dimensionless groups involving the bridge physics. Four approaches to derive the scaling rules are discussed in the following.

4.3.1. Weber number-based scaling

The Weber number can be defined as the ratio of the kinetic energy density to the capillary stress as:

$$We = \frac{\rho_p R_p v^2}{\gamma \cos \theta} = \frac{\rho_p R_p (\Omega D)^2 / 4}{\gamma \cos \theta} \quad (30)$$

where $v = \Omega D/2$ is the velocity of the flowing particles, estimated as the angular velocity of the drum, Ω , times the drum radius, $D/2$ [44, 45].

Considering an invariant average velocity in the original and CG simulations, in order to keep the Weber number constant, the surface tension γ should scale with $\ell \gamma_{CG} = \ell \gamma$ like R_p . As the capillary force is also proportional to the radius of the particles R_p [29], this will lead to ℓ^2 scaling of the liquid bridge force.

The Capillary number is defined by:

$$Ca = \frac{\eta v_c}{\gamma} \quad (31)$$

where η and v_c are the liquid viscosity and particle characteristic velocity ($v_c \sim \Omega D/2$). To derive a scaling rule for the viscous term of the liquid bridge force, the capillary number must be kept constant, resulting in ℓ scaling of the liquid viscosity η . Consequently, based on Eq. (8), the ℓ^2 scaling of the viscous force will be consistent with the scaling of the capillary term (ℓ^2 times).

4.3.2. Bond number-based scaling

The classical Bond number is defined as the ratio of the capillary force to the single particle weight [10] as:

$$Bo_g = F_c / F_g = \frac{6\gamma \cos \theta}{4R_p^2 g \rho_p} \quad (32)$$

which can be interpreted as the ratio of the cohesive stress to the single particle gravitational stress. Thus, in order to have a constant Bond number in both CG and original systems, the liquid surface tension (γ) should be ℓ^2 scaled to compensate R_p^2 . Consequently, ℓ^3 scaling of the cohesive force will be obtained (as capillary force is proportional to R_p). In order to keep the Ca number constant, the viscosity η must be scaled ℓ^2 times, resulting in a consistent ℓ^3 scaling of the viscous force. The contact force must be scaled ℓ^3 times to ensure consistency with the cohesive force scaling, that is, the contact stiffness and damping coefficient must be scaled ℓ^2 and $\ell^{2.5}$ times, respectively [10].

Table 3
Summary of the scaling rules derived based on dimensionless groups.

Scaling basis ^a	γ	η	k	c	f	T
We, Bo_p , Bo_γ , Ag	ℓ	ℓ	ℓ	ℓ^2	ℓ^2	ℓ^3
Bo_g	ℓ^2	ℓ^2	ℓ^2	$\ell^{2.5}$	ℓ^3	ℓ^4

^a Columns from left to right correspond to the liquid surface tension γ , liquid viscosity η , contact stiffness (normal and tangential), contact damping coefficient (normal and tangential), interparticle force (contact and liquid bridge), and torque. Note that the scaling of the interparticle force (f) and torque (T) result from the scaling of the parameters on the left.

4.3.3. Agglomerate number-based scaling

LaMarche et al. [43] define a new dimensionless number, namely the Agglomerate number, as

$$Ag = \frac{v_{crit}^2}{3T_g}, \quad (33)$$

where v_{crit} , the minimum, relative (normal), pre-collisional velocity required to avoid pair-sticking is

$$v_{crit}^2 = \frac{2W(1 - e_n^2)}{me_n^2}, \quad (34)$$

and W is the integral of the cohesive force over the separation distance. In order to keep Ag constant, for a model that conserves the velocity fluctuations across the scales, with a constant restitution coefficient (e_n), v_{crit}^2 should remain invariant. Thus, W should be scaled as m , since W/m is expected to be invariant. This will result in ℓ^2 scaling of the cohesive force considering geometric similarity of the separation distance (see Section 4.2). The resulting scaling rules are thus the same as those derived for the We-based scaling. However, as discussed in Section 3, T_g is not invariant and therefore Ag is neither. However, such discussion goes beyond the scope of this study.

4.3.4. Shear bond number-based scaling

LaMarche et al. [43] discuss that for dense systems with enduring contacts, a force-based description is more appropriate than the energy-based one as in Section 4.3.3. They define the Bond number as $Bo = F_c / F_{sys}$ where F_c is related to the magnitude and type of cohesion and F_{sys} is a system characteristic force. For a simple shear flow, the shear Bond number can be defined alternatively as

$$Bo_\gamma = F_c / \rho_p \dot{\gamma}^2 R^4 \quad (35)$$

where $\dot{\gamma}R$ is the shear velocity. Bo_γ can be interpreted as the cohesive stress to shear kinetic stress and leads to a similar scaling as the Weber-based scaling.

4.3.5. Pressure bond number-based scaling

Roy et al. [36] have defined the relevant Bond number for a shear cell under gravity as the ratio of the cohesive stress to the local confining stress, as

$$Bo_p = F_c / p_{mean} R^2 \quad (36)$$

which also leads to the Weber-based scaling, considering that the local pressure in the system should be the same in the original and CG systems.

Table 3 presents a summary of the scaling rules derived based on the discussed dimensionless numbers.

Fig. 4. Comparison of Weber-based and Bo-based scaling approaches, (a) Snapshots of the drum simulations with original wet particles ($Bo_g = 14.6$), Weber-based CG3, and Bond-based CG3 (left to right). The colouring is based on the magnitude of the velocity of the particles relative to the drum velocity, (b) Evolution of the centre of mass of the particles in the drum for the cases in (a).

4.3.6. Discussion on scaling rules for wet particle systems

Fig. 4(a) shows snapshots of DEM simulations in the rotating drum for original particles, particles coarse grained 3 times CG3 with parameters scaled based on the Weber number and on the classical Bond number. The results indicate that the CG simulation based on Weber number scaling is in better agreement with the original DEM simulation both qualitatively (Fig. 4(a)), and quantitatively where the evolution of the centre of mass is considered (Fig. 4(b)). Additionally, Fig. 4(a) indicates that both the bulk shape and velocity profile have considerable deviations when the Bond number based scaling is used.

As discussed before, dimensionless groups We , Ag , Bo_γ , and Bo_p , will result in the same scaling rule for the liquid bridge force. In fact, in energy dominated systems such as the fluidized bed, as previously reported by Tausendschön et al. [10], or in confined systems like a rotating drum, the classical Bond number, Bo_g , leads to an over-prediction of cohesive forces. Instead of Bo_g , one should use the appropriate definitions of the Bond number based on the existing

system state, either Eqs. (35), (36) or the energy-based Ag number, Eq. (33).

A detailed quantitative comparison of the We-number based CG-DEM simulations against the original particle simulations in the rolling and slumping regime is presented in the next section.

5. Results and discussion

In this section, the results of the CG-DEM simulations are presented for dry particles in the rolling, and for wet particles in the rolling and the wet slumping regimes. The results presented for the wet particles in this section are based on constant liquid bridge volume and constant Weber number.

5.1. CG for dry particles: Effect of restitution coefficient scaling

Figs. 5(a) to 5(d) compare the bulk density, velocity, strain rate, and granular temperature profiles, in the original particle simulations

Fig. 5. Profiles of (a) volume fraction (b) bulk relative velocity to the drum velocity in x -direction (c) deviatoric strain rate (d) granular temperature in a slice of the drum (shown in Fig. 3(a)). Symbols represent different CG with constant e , while lines and symbols refer to systems with restitution coefficient scaled, based on the model proposed by Nakamura et al. [15]. For all sub-plots, lines and symbols follow the same legend as in plot (a).

and the CG simulations for dry particles in a rotating drum. The quantities are calculated along the y -direction in a slice of the granular bed (Fig. 3(a)). The scaling of the restitution coefficient, e , proposed by Nakamura et al. [15], is compared with the case of constant restitution coefficient. While the bulk volume fraction is not much affected by the different e scaling, the velocity and the strain rate profile of the CG simulation with scaled e show a better agreement with the original particle simulation. This means that the viscous force scaling resulting from the scaling of the restitution coefficient leads to better reproducibility of the system's flow behaviour. Regarding the granular temperature, only a qualitative systematic improvement is observed when the scaling of e is adapted. While the granular temperature profile in the flowing zone ($0.02 < y < 0.06$), shows a better agreement with the original particle system, the profile adjacent to the wall, in the more static regime, does not. Comparing the scaled and unscaled systems, higher values of granular temperature are observed in the flowing zone, although the scaled system has higher restitution coefficient. This suggests that the granular temperature is not only dependent on the dissipation at the contacts via the restitution coefficient. Rather, the collision frequency might play an important role, as it depends not only on T_g but also on density and coordination number. Overly strong damping in the unscaled system can reduce the number of new contacts/collisions, leading to less dissipation and higher granular temperature compared with the scaled case, where higher relative

motion of the particles increases the number of collisions. As additional note, only when zooming in to the volume fraction profile, one can see small variations that also reflect the trends visible in the velocity gradient and granular temperature profiles.

5.2. CG for wet particles: Rolling regime

In this section, a detailed quantitative study of CG simulations using Weber number-based scaling is reported for different values of surface tension varying from 0–0.073 N/m. In order to ensure the validity of the viscous force scaling, a detailed analysis of CG systems with high liquid viscosity (and low surface tension) are presented in Appendix B, where their flow behaviour is compared with the original particle system.

Fig. 6 shows the velocity of the particles in systems with different attractive forces. While the free surface shape changes with surface tension, the velocities of the up-scaled CG systems are in good agreement with the original.

To quantitatively compare the evolution of the particle bed, Fig. 7 shows the average horizontal component of the particles' velocity versus the vertical y position for the original and CG systems in the slice shown in Fig. 3(a) ($0.120 < x < 0.124$ m). The velocity profile of the CG particles is in good agreement with the original system for all values of surface tension, with some differences at $y \sim 0.02$ and at the free surfaces. The convergence with the drum velocity at $y = 0$, indicates

Fig. 6. Snapshots of the simulation for the original particles system, CG2, and CG3 (left to right) in the (a) dry case ($\gamma = 0$, $Bo_g = 0.0$), (b) wet case ($\gamma = 0.036$ N/m, $Bo_g = 7.3$), and (c) wet case ($\gamma = 0.073$ N/m, $Bo_g = 14.6$).

that no slip occurs between wall and particle bed, due to the baffles. Next, we consider the horizontal velocity relative to the rotating drum in Fig. 8. As the surface tension increases, the velocity magnitude of the particles at the free surface decreases. The dry system develops an avalanche with steady velocity gradient while the wet cases have zero velocity gradient.

Fig. 9 shows the average volume fraction of the particles along the y -coordinate in the drum slice, for the same systems in Figs. 6–8. As the surface tension increases, the volume fraction decreases. This is in agreement with the results by Shi et al. [39] where the same relative dilation is observed for high friction coefficients, ($\mu_p = 0.9$ in this study, see Table 1). Moreover, good agreement is found among the volume fractions for different CG with CG3 deviating most.

Fig. 10 shows the effect of surface tension on the deviatoric strain rate for the same dataset. Good agreement is found, with the original case showing a more detailed wiggly structure. The results indicate that dry particles, $\gamma = 0$, experience the highest strain rate at the surface. In the wet systems, the maximum strain rate is observed in the centre. The same trends can be observed in Fig. 11, showing the evolution of the granular temperature with height. While the granular temperature overall increases with height for the dry system, it decreases in the wet particle system, after reaching a maximum in the

shear band. The decrease in strain rate and granular temperature close to the surface is possibly due to the formation of particle clusters as a result of the presence of the liquid bridges. Comparing the granular temperature of the CG particles with the original particles, serious deviations can be observed. This has previously been reported by Radl et al. [11] and Benyahia and Galvin [42] for shear flow systems as well. This deviation can be explained by the fact that when a group of original particles is represented by a CG particle, the internal fluctuation motions within one CG particle are neglected. Such relative motions present in the original particle system, lead to a higher dissipation of energy, and as a result to a lower granular temperature.

Fig. 12 shows the effect of particle scale up on the deviatoric stress vs. pressure, where the slope of the line is the macroscopic friction, Eq. (17). When the system is cohesive, the locus consists of two regions with different slopes. The region with the lower slope (lower macroscopic friction) corresponds to data close to the free surface, where the pressure is low. By increasing the surface tension in the system, particles undergo a lower deviatoric stress at low pressure. A similar trend is observed for CG particle, showing that upscaled simulations conserve the macroscopic friction. However, the region with higher slope (at large P) seems to be down-shifted, relative to the dry case.

Fig. 7. Velocity profiles in the selected slice of the drum, as shown in Fig. 3(a) ($0.120 < x < 0.124$ m). The stars refer to the velocity of the drum in the x-direction; refer to the legend in (a).

Fig. 8. Relative velocity profiles in the selected slice of the drum ($0.120 < x < 0.124$ m); refer to the legend in (a).

Fig. 9. Volume fraction profiles in the selected slice of the drum ($0.120 < x < 0.124$ m); the dashed line represents $\phi = 0.58$; refer to the legend in (a).

Fig. 13 compares the apparent viscosity η , i.e., the ratio of deviatoric stress to deviatoric shear strain, against the inertial number I for CG and original particle systems and different surface tensions. In the dry system, η decreases monotonically with increasing I , which suggests that the dry non-cohesive particle system has a shear thinning behaviour. For finite surface tension, a second branch starts to appear, $\gamma = 0.036$ N/m, and is fully developed for $\gamma = 0.073$ N/m. In contrast to

the dry particles system, wet systems show a reduced shear thinning range with I , as the cohesion increases. This is due to the relative dilation observed in Fig. 9, i.e., the higher the cohesion, the lower the volume fraction, leading to a decrease in the bulk viscosity. These features are well reproduced by the CG simulations, that is, In fact, the rheological behaviour of the system, can be properly captured by using CG particles.

Fig. 10. Deviatoric strain rate profiles in the selected slice of the drum, Eq. (18); refer to the legend in (a).

Fig. 11. Granular temperature profiles in the selected slice of the drum, Eq. (14); refer to the legend in (a).

Fig. 12. Deviatoric stress plotted against pressure in the selected slice of the drum. The dashed lines represent the fitted line (linear correlation) for the dry case in plot (a); refer to the legend in (a).

5.2.1. Effect of CG on the wall coverage ratio with wet particles

In this section, the effect of CG on the wall coverage with wet particles ($\gamma = 0.073 \text{ N/m}$) is investigated. Counting the particles sticking to the wall is misleading, both concerning numbers, N_{stick}^{CG} , or fractions, $f_{stick} = N_{stick}^{CG} / N_{total}^{CG}$ (data not shown), showing an increasing trend for f_{stick} with an increase in CG ratio. Fig. 14(a) shows snapshots of the CG and original particle system at $t = 9.95 \text{ s}$. To compare the surface coverage in these snapshots, the evolution of the percentage of the

wall area covered with sticky wet particles is presented in Fig. 14(b), with $P_a = 100\% \times \frac{N_{stick} \pi R^2}{A_{wall}}$ (overlaps ignored). All data (CG) show an increasing trend with time. Furthermore, the wall area coverage decreases with increasing CG ratio, i.e. the original particles cover a larger area of the wall compared with CG2 and CG3. This observation can be due to the fact that Bo_g number is the appropriate dimensionless number when it comes to the single particle layer attached to the wall, and CG3 particles have a lower Bo_g number than the CG2 and the

Fig. 13. Apparent viscosity-inertia number plots in the selected slice of the drum; refer to the legend in (a); data from this and previous figures are from Fig. 6.

original particles in the We-based scaling. As a result, they have more tendency to detach from the wall and fall. Looking at the enlarged wall section in Fig. 14(a), there are more CG3 particles with high velocity magnitude, which corresponds to their tendency for falling from the wall due to a lower Bo_g number than the original and CG2 particles.

For more information about the effect of increasing Bo_g on the wall coverage (CG3 system), see Appendix C.

5.2.2. CG for wet particles with variable liquid bridge volume

While in the previous section, the liquid was homogeneously distributed, next, we focus on liquid transport. Different mechanisms can contribute to the liquid re-distribution in the system, namely convection and liquid migration.

• Liquid convection

In order to compare the liquid convection pattern in the original and the CG systems, a spray zone is defined, in which the particles receive a given amount of liquid. In either systems, the ratio of liquid film volume (V_f) to particle volume (V_p) is set to $V_f/V_p = 0.05$, meaning that $V_{f,CG} = \ell^3 V_f$. Fig. 15 shows the initial state of the inserted particles being subjected to the circular spray zone, and snapshots of the original and CG systems, coloured based on V_f/V_p . A similar pattern for the liquid convection can be seen in the original and CG systems. In addition, the evolution of the centre of mass motion of the liquid in the bulk $\langle r_b \rangle = \frac{\sum V_{b,ij} \times r_{b,ij}}{\sum V_{b,ij}}$ (where $V_{b,ij}$ is the volume of the liquid bridge formed between particles i and j , and $r_{b,ij}$ is the distance between the centre of the bridge and the reference point of (0,0,0)), is shown in Fig. 16.

The figure confirms that the liquid in the CG systems have a similar convective motion pattern and can predict the centre of mass of the liquid in the drum quite well, besides small differences between extrema. For larger CG, the liquid centre moves slightly earlier.

• Liquid migration (diffusion in volume distribution space V_f/V_p)

In addition to the convective motion of the liquid, as a result of the particles' bulk motion, the local liquid migration among the particles, based on the model of Mani et al. [26], see Section 2.1, is investigated in the CG and original particle simulations. To compare the liquid migration in the CG system with the original particle system, the histogram of V_f/V_p is presented in Fig. 17. In this figure, the vertical axis, f_N , represents the normalized number of particles, i.e. the ratio of the particles with a certain liquid volume V_f/V_p to the total number of particles in the system. The bar at $V_f/V_p = 0$ corresponds to the particles

unaffected by the spray zone. Overall, the histograms of the CG systems are in qualitative agreement with the original particles, with deviations at $0.0 < V_f/V_p < 0.025$. In fact, by increasing the CG ratio, the number of dry particles (relative to the initial number of CG particles) decreases, as the number of particles with $0.0 < V_f/V_p < 0.025$ increases. There are two reasons for this observation. The first one is the deviations in the strain rate profile, shown in Fig. 10, meaning that the CG3 particles with higher strain rate, can transfer the liquid to a higher number of dry particles in the system. The second reason is that, as presented in Appendix D., CG3 profile of the averaged number of contacts per particle, shows more fluctuations compared with the CG1 and CG2 systems.

The spatial diffusion is not addressed in this work. For a more mathematical treatment of convection and diffusion of liquid, see [46], which goes beyond the scope of the present paper.

5.3. CG for wet particles: Wet slumping regime

To investigate the applicability of the CG model in another regime beyond rolling, the number of particles, rotational velocity of the drum, and the liquid surface tension are increased relative to Section 5.2, namely $N_p = 468,000$, $We = 0.2$, and $Bo_g = 29.2$ (CG1). In order to understand the more transient, non-steady behaviour of the system in this regime, the evolution of the centroid angle is studied, i.e. the angle between the vertical line passing through the drum centre and the line connecting the centre to the centre of mass of the bulk, as defined in [47].

Fig. 18 compares the evolution of the centroid angle over time for different CG ratios up to CG5. The results indicate a good agreement between the CG and the original particle systems in terms of the evolution of the centroid angle.

Fig. 19 represents snapshots of the drum with CG1 to CG3 particles at different times of the simulation. The corresponding times and the centroid angle of each snapshot are shown in Fig. 18. It can be observed that while the particle bulks in different CG scales show a good qualitative agreement in the first and the second snapshots, falling of the slumps, i.e. the third snapshot, which are avalanches breaking away along a curved surface and collapsing downhill with some rotation in the drum rotation direction [25], happens with a short delay in different CG systems. In fact, this is one of the challenges when comparing the behaviour of original and CG particles in the wet slumping regime.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 14. (a) Snapshots of the drum with CG1, CG2, and CG3 particles with wall cohesion ($\gamma = 0.073$ N/m) at $t = 9.95$ s, (b) Evolution of the drum wall percentage covered by adhered particles.

Since in this regime the angle behaves periodically, next, the discrete to continuum averaging is done within one full period for, e.g., 3.5–7.5 s. In order to ensure that the results are independent of the size of the grids, the averaging with two different bin sizes are compared in the following.

Fig. 20 shows the profile of the volume fraction for different CG systems. The profiles are very similar for different bin sizes. While the volume fraction of the CG2 and CG3 systems are in good agreement with the original particles, scaling up to CG4 and CG5 reduces the resolution, not showing the dip in the middle height region. The main reason for the detected behaviour in Fig. 20 is having a noisier dataset for CG4 and CG5, due to insufficient number of particles in the system for higher CG. This leads to the loss of resolution in particular areas

when averaging is done (see Appendix E.).

Fig. 21 represents the relative velocity profiles of the particles in the drum. The data collapse up to a certain height, $y \approx 0.05$ m. CG particle systems deviate from the original at intermediate height and approach again closer to the free surface. This is possibly related to differences in the velocity of the falling slumps. Looking at Figs. 22 and 23, which show the change in the granular temperature and the deviatoric strain rate with height in the selected slice, the same trends can be observed. Comparing Fig. 22 with the relevant plot in the rolling regime (Fig. 11), while increasing the CG ratio in the rolling regime leads to an increase in the granular temperature, in the wet slumping regime, original particles (CG1) indicate a much higher granular temperature than the CG particle systems. This contrasting behaviour can be due

Fig. 15. Initial spray zone in the drum with floating particles, at $t = 0$ s, before settling (top). Snapshot of the original and CG systems (CG1, CG2, and CG3 systems, from left to right), at $t = 9.95$ s, i.e. 0.72 revolutions, coloured based on the dimensionless liquid volume on each particle (V_f/V_p).

Fig. 16. Evolution of the centre of mass of the liquid in the drum (r_b).

to the sudden increase of the strain rate around $y = 0.11$ m, which we attribute to the falling of the slumps with a higher velocity. These results suggest that in contrast to the rolling regime where CG works very well, some limitations for CG exist in more transient and dynamic regimes, such as wet slumping.

6. Summary and conclusion

In the present work, coarse-grain DEM models based on parameter scaling are studied for dense sheared granular system in a rotating drum, with dry and wet particles. Firstly, upscaling in the dry case in the slow, dense rolling regime is discussed. For given CG upscaling factor ℓ , and based on constant We number, forces are scaled quadratically

(ℓ^2), with constant coefficient of restitution. CG successfully matches the macroscopic fields, including density, velocity, deviatoric strain rate, bulk friction, and bulk viscosity, but not the granular temperature T_g . The scaling for the restitution coefficient proposed by Nakamura et al. [15] shows better agreement between original and CG cases, not perfect, however. More appropriate scaling for the restitution coefficient should be considered for dry, dense particle systems under shear.

Subsequently, CG-DEM simulations for the wet case are studied, focusing on the scaling of liquid bridge related parameters, including liquid bridge volume, rupture distance, and cohesive force. Two different scaling strategies for the cohesive force were investigated, either based on the Weber or the Bond dimensionless numbers. Classical Bo_g (gravity single particle-force based) does not work, while Bo_p (local confining pressure based) does, being identical to We. The quadratic (ℓ^2) scaling of the liquid bridge force, resulting from the Weber-based scaling, leads to good agreements with the original system in the rolling regime, whereas Bo-based scaling leads to overly strong cohesion.

In addition, novel insights are: (1) for inhomogeneous liquid distribution (spray), both convective and migration (diffusion) patterns of the liquid in the CG systems agree mostly with the original particle simulations (differences for weakly wetted particles). (2) The original particles cover a larger surface area of the wall compared to the CG particles, due to having a higher Bo number (in We-based scaling). This finding suggests that developing an advanced CG model with region-dependent scaling rules could be of great significance in systems where different regions have different physics (bulk vs. wall contacts), and can be a future-subject of study.

Evaluating the agreement of the CG and original simulations in the wet slumping regime is more challenging, due to a periodic, non-smooth, slumpy behaviour of clustered particles in the system. Nevertheless, by analysing a single period, the CG simulations show good agreement with the original system up to CG3, but serious deviations for CG4 and CG5. Mostly localized in the bulk middle area, deviations

Fig. 17. Histogram of the particles' liquid volume ratio V_l/V_p in (a) CG1, (b) CG2, and (c) CG3 systems, at $t = 9.95$ s.

Fig. 18. Evolution of the centroid angle in the wet slumping regime. The corresponding snapshots at the dashed lines (a), (b), and (c) are later shown in Fig. 19.

are associated with the high noise due to the limited number of particles per bin.

To conclude, the proposed upscaling model is capable of reproducing the rheological behaviour of dense particulate system under shear with high accuracy and considerably lower computational cost, if appropriate scaling rules are applied. The fields are reproduced well by upscaled CG simulations for density, velocity, strain rate, macroscopic friction, and apparent viscosity, but not for granular temperature. Increasing the CG ratio leads to larger T_g in the slow dense rolling regime. However, the opposite trend is observed in the more dynamic wet slumping regime.

The effect of restitution coefficient scaling on the granular temperature, in such an overly damped state, is not fully clear and needs

further investigations. The proposed scalings for the restitution coefficient by Nakamura et al. [15]; Xu et al. [48], show inconsistencies for systems with low restitution coefficient. Therefore, our ongoing work focuses on developing an improved version of this scaling rule, valid for all $0 < e < 1$.

The effect of CG on granule (agglomerate) size distribution (GSD), which is an important aspect in wet granulation system, is an ongoing work. Furthermore, a more detailed CG-DEM study of systems with high Ca, also including both tangential and normal terms of the viscous force, is a possible subject of future work. The applicability of CG modelling for liquid migration and convection mechanisms in other regimes and systems (dilute, dynamic) remains an open question.

Fig. 19. Snapshots of the wet slumping regime in the drum with original CG1, CG2, and CG3 particles from left to right. The corresponding centroid angle of the snapshots (a), (b), and (c) is indicated by the dashed lines in Fig. 18.

Fig. 20. Volume fraction profile for different CG ratios and bin widths (w_{bin}), with data from Fig. 18, averaged from $t = 3.5-7.5$ s.

Fig. 21. Relative velocity profiles for data from Fig. 20.

Fig. 22. Granular temperature profiles for data from Fig. 20.

Fig. 23. Deviatoric strain rate profiles for data from Fig. 20.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Roxana Saghafian Larijani: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Vanessa Magnanimo:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Stefan Luding:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Parametric study

In order to get a better understanding of the effect of process and material parameters on the flow of the particles in the drum for setting up the simulations (Section 2.2), the parametric study presented in this section (Fig. A.24) has been performed.

(a) Surface tension has a considerable effect on the velocity profile at the free surface, i.e. decrease in particles velocity by increase of the surface tension. In addition, the more the surface tension is increased, the more increase in the height of the slice can be observed, which

Fig. A.24. Parametric study on the effect of (a) surface tension, (b) liquid bridge volume, (c) drum angular velocity, (d) particle friction coefficient, and (e) the baffle height, on the velocity profile of the selected slice in the drum (as shown in Fig. 3(a)).

Fig. B.25. Velocity profiles in the selected slice of the drum.

is due to reduced density and the formation of a large cluster in the system. Increasing (b) liquid bridge volume leads to the same trend, decreasing v_x . The increase, either in (c) drum angular velocity or (d) particle friction coefficient, leads to an increase in the particles velocity at the free surface. While the presence of baffles can avoid slipping of the particles at the wall, the velocity profile does not have a considerable sensitivity on (e) height of the baffles.

Appendix B. Validation of liquid bridge viscous force scaling

Fig. B.25 complements Section 5.2. and presents the velocity profiles of the original and CG particles in systems with high Ca number. The results suggest that the CG particles velocity profile agrees well with the original particles system profile, even for liquid viscosities much larger than used in the main paper.

Appendix C. Effect of Bo number on the percentage of the wall coverage by wet particles

Fig. C.26 presents the effect of Bond number on the wall coverage to complement Section 5.2.1. The plots with circles and squares represent the systems with $Bo_g < 1$ and $Bo_g > 1$, respectively. An interesting effect of the wall cohesion is that increasing Bo_g , leads to an increase in the wall coverage. However, when $Bo_g > 1$, an opposite trend can be observed, the wall coverage decreases as Bo_g rises. In systems with $Bo_g < 1$, increasing cohesion helps the particles to overcome the effect of gravity, and not to detach. However, for $Bo_g > 1$, increasing the surface tension and as a result the Bo_g , the particle–particle cohesion in the bulk increases at the same time. Consequently, more particles will attach to the bulk and not to the wall, which leads to a decrease in the wall coverage.

Fig. C.26. Evolution of the wall surface coverage by wet particles.

Fig. D.27. Averaged number of contacts per particle profile in the selected slice of the drum.

Appendix D. Number of contacts per particle profile

To understand the effect of CG on the liquid migration (see Section 5.2.2), the profile of the number of contacts per particle in the original and CG systems is presented in Fig. D.27. The average number of contacts per particle remains constant among the original and CG systems. However, the CG3 profile shows more fluctuations, which is one reason for the differences observed in the liquid migration

behaviour of the systems, shown in Fig. 17.

Appendix E. Time evolution of the volume fraction in the wet slumping regime

To explore further the observation in Fig. 20, Fig. E.28 compares the volume fraction in the selected slice in the original, CG3 and CG5 systems. Each line in the plot corresponds to a particular phase in the

Fig. E.28. Time evolution of volume fraction in the selected slice of the drum, for (a) CG1; (b) CG3; (c) CG5. Different phases are indicated by the colorbar.

simulation, so that the evolution of the volume fraction profile over time can be observed. The dip survives time averaging for CG1 and CG3.

Data availability

The data is distributed under an open-source creative commons licence in a 4TU-ResearchData software (<http://doi.org/10.4121/3762f6a1-c26b-4ec7-b005-adf14b376831>).

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